

Description of A Patient with Secondary Amenorrhea and Hirsutism

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ABSTRACT

Hirsutism is common in acromegaly. Together with Secondary oligomenorrhea, it makes the physicians think about different disorders. Usually, clinicians relate those complaints in female patients of reproductive age to Polycystic ovarian syndrome(PCOS). We are describing a 26-year-old Indian-American female who was diagnosed and treated by the Obstetrics and Gynecology department as having PCOS and treated with transdermal birth control patches. She self-referred to our endocrinologist for further investigation and treatment because of a lack of improvement of her secondary amenorrhea and new onset of headache, as well as increased sweating and weight gain. On further questioning, she admitted to having mild increments in the last 6 months in the size of her fingers and puffiness of her feet. The workup confirmed the presence of acromegaly. The patient had elevated insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) twice on separate days and was non-suppressible after the oral glucose tolerance test growth hormone (GH). An MRI of the brain showed a right pituitary macroadenoma. The tumor had a mild extension to the right cavernous sinuses. Her serum total testosterone, androstenedione, and dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate (DHEAS) were normal, with elevated free testosterone levels and low sex hormone-binding globulin. There were no polycystic ovaries, and the endometrial strip was low-normal (2 mm). We attributed her hirsutism to high-free testosterone and not to PCOS, and her secondary amenorrhea was caused by secondary hypogonadism due to GH-secreting pituitary macroadenoma. The patient underwent transsphenoidal resection of the pituitary macroadenoma, and the histology confirmed GH-secreting adenoma. This case presentation intends to highlight that in patients with secondary amenorrhea and hirsutisms, the differential diagnosis is broad. It should include, besides PCOS, congenital adrenal hyperplasia, Cushing's syndrome, adrenal and ovarian tumors, and acromegaly, among other possibilities. As we know, the diagnosis of acromegaly is made on average 5-10 years after the initiation of the disease. We made the diagnosis of acromegaly 6- months after the complaints of the patient started. The pituitary GH-secreting macroadenoma was removed by an experienced neurosurgeon. This case underscores the investigation of subtle features of acromegaly and recognizes that secondary amenorrhea and hirsutism can be attributed to other disease states besides PCOS.

Keywords: Acromegaly; Hirsutism; Secondary amenorrhea; Insulin-like growth factor 1; Growth hormone; Macroadenoma; Polycystic ovarian syndrome

INTRODUCTION

In female patients of reproductive age, hirsutism and oligomenorrhea are frequently attributed to PCOS [1,2]. We need to remember that idiopathic PCOS is a diagnosis of exclusion [3,4]. Other causes of hirsutism might be idiopathic hyperandrogenism (15%), idiopathic hirsutism (10%), non-classic congenital adrenal hyperplasia (3%), prolactinoma, and rarely hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism.

Acromegaly is caused by chronic hypersecretion of growth hormone and insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1). The disease causes an increase in the size of the hands and feet, coarse features of the face, and multiple cardiovascular, respiratory, musculoskeletal, and malignant complications. It is usually caused by a pituitary-secreting adenoma. Because the diagnosis is usually made later, in general at least 5-10 years after disease onset, the pituitary tumors causing the disease are large macroadenomas [5]. Acromegaly is a rare disease. The scientists estimate that about 3 to 14 of every 100,000 people have been diagnosed with it [6,7]. To make the diagnosis of these disorders early, we need to think about it in patients presenting with hirsutism and oligomenorrhea and have a diagnosis of PCOS, as up to 50% of patients with acromegaly might also have non-idiopathic PCOS. We also need to look for other non-specific features of the disease, like increased sweating, headaches, and carpal tunnel syndrome, to make the diagnosis early [7,8]. Half of the patients with acromegaly have hypogonadism which is caused by the direct mass effect on gonadotropic cells of GH-secreting tumor and through increased levels of prolactin. The mechanism of hirsutism in acromegaly is usually associated with insulin resistance, and increased insulin levels, which leads to a decrease in sex hormone-binding globulin, and increased free testosterone levels, as well as stimulating the production of ovarian androgens [9]. The mortality rate of acromegaly is 2-3 times higher. The leading causes of death in patients with untreated acromegaly are cardiovascular diseases, respiratory complications, and increased malignancy rates [8]. With early diagnosis and appropriate treatment, the patients might have a normal life expectancy.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 26-year-old Indian-American female presented with complaints of a 6-month history of amenorrhea and increased hair growth on her face and body. Menarche occurred at the age of 13, and the menstrual periods were regular until six months ago. Breast development was normal. Her increased hair growth, which was distressing to her, started around six months ago and necessitated weekly shaving. She had a history of major depressive disorder (MDD) treated with Vortioxetine 5 mg per day by a psychiatrist, which is a serotonin modulator. She was also diagnosed by OBGYN specialists as having polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) and treated with weekly patches of norelgestromin/ethinyl estradiol (150/35 mcg per day) and metformin ER (500 mg/day). The patient complained of headaches for 3 months, increased sweating, dizziness, and weakness. The patient self-referred to our clinical endocrinologist for further investigation in the late winter of 2023. On further questioning, she admitted in the last 6 months to increased puffiness of her feet, hand size, face puffiness, tongue size, hirsutism, and headache. She also complained of insomnia, pain in her hands, and numbness in her fingers, especially after sleep.

On physical examination, she was normotensive with a BMI of 27.3 kg/m², and her blood pressure was normal. She had mildly coarse facial features with mild puffiness of the face, a prominent chin, macroglossia, a woody nose, and bullous lips. She had significant terminal hair growth on her face, abdomen, and legs with

a Ferriman-Gallwey score of 36. She did not have acanthosis nigricans or skin tags. She had positive Phalen and Hoffman-Tinel signs as well as numbness in the first three and a half fingers, especially during the night, suggesting carpal tunnel syndrome. Her hands and feet were puffy, and she admitted to increasing her ring size in the last 6 months. She had mild enlargement of the thyroid with questionable nodules. She had no abdominal masses and no cushingoid features.

Notably, a laboratory work-up revealed a normal dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate (DHEAS) of 322 mcg/dl (84-378), a low luteinizing hormone (LH) of 0.7 IU/l (1.09-9.2), a follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) of 0.4 IU/L (4.4-21.5), and estradiol of less than 5 pg/ml, suggesting secondary hypogonadism. The prolactin (PrL) level was also low at 1.8 ng/ml (4.8-23.3). The patient had secondary hypothyroidism with free thyroxine (FT4) of 0.61 ng/dl (0.76-1.46) and normal thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) of 0.78 ng/dl (0.36-3.74). The serum pregnancy test was negative. In the morning at 8 a.m., cortisol was normal at 19.2 mcg/dl, as was the morning adrenocorticotropic hormone at 45.9 pg/ml (7.2-63.3). 17-hydroxyprogesterone was normal at 37 ng/dl (35-199 ng/dl). Total morning testosterone was normal twice for females at 20 ng/dl and 22 ng/dl (13-71) on two separate days, but the free testosterone level measured by equilibrium dialysis was elevated two times on separate days at 4.3 pg/ml and 4.5 pg/ml (0-4). Sex-hormone binding globulin was low at 12 nmol/l (20-130). Her glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1C) was normal at 5.5%.

Insulin growth factor-1(IGF-1) was two times on separate days elevated- 594 ng/ml and 695 ng/ml (91-308) for her age and gender and the Growth hormone (GH) at baseline was 5 ng/ml. After 75 grams of glucose per mouth, her 2-hour oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) failed to suppress the GH below 1 ng/ml. It was 3 ng/ml the first hour and 10 ng/ml the second hour confirming biochemically the diagnosis of Acromegaly. Serum phosphorus level was elevated at 5.5 mg/dl (2.5-4.8) and the 3-hour postprandial C-peptide was also elevated at 6.6 ng/ml (1.1-4.4). Fasting blood glucose was normal at 93 mg/dl and 2 hours post-OGTT was in normal ranges- 110 mg/dl (Table 1).

	Patient value	Normal value
DHEAS	322 mcg/dl	84-378 mcg/dl
LH	0.7IU/l	1.09-9.2 IU/l
FSH	0.4 IU/L	4.4-21.5 IU/L
Estradiol	<5pg/ml	30-400 pg/ml
Prolactin	1.8 ng/ml	4.8-23.3 ng/ml
Free T4	0.61 ng/dl	0.76-1.46 ng/dl
TSH	0.78 ng/dl	0.36-3.74 ng/dl
AM Cortisol	19.2 mcg/dl	5-25 mcg/dl
AM ACTH	45.9 pg/ml	7.2-63.3 pg/ml
17-hydroxyprogesterone	50 ng/dl	45-1185 ng/dl
Total morning testosterone Day 1	20 ng/dl	13-71 ng/dl
Total morning testosterone Day 2	22ng/dl	13-71 ng/dl
Free testosterone level day 1	4.3 pg/ml	0-4 pg/ml
Free testosterone level day 2	4.5 pg/ml	0-4 pg/ml
Sex- hormone binding globulin	12 nmol/l	20-130 nmol/l

Table 1: Hormone lab values

DHEAS, Dehydroxyepiandrosterone; LH, Luteinizing hormone; FSH, Follicle- stimulating hormone; Free T4, Free thyroxine; TSH, Thyroid- stimulating hormone; AM ACTH, morning Adrenocorticotropic hormone; HbA1c-Hemoglobin A1C; GH, Growth hormone; OGTT, Oral Glucose tolerance test

A pelvic ultrasound identified normal ovaries and a low normal endometrial strip of 2 millimeters additionally inconsistent with the diagnosis of polycystic ovarian syndrome. The sleep study was negative for sleep apnea and Echocardiogram was normal.

MRI of the brain showed a right pituitary macroadenoma with mild extension to the right cavernous sinuses and deviation of the pituitary stalk to the left (Figure 1). The macroadenoma had an extension into the suprasellar region with a mass effect on the right optic chiasm without compromising the visual fields. The neuroophthalmologist did not find a visual field defect.

Figure 1; MRI of the hypophyseal area.

The sonogram of the thyroid showed goiter with bilateral thyroid cysts measuring 2.2/2.6/1.7 mm on the right and 2.6/2.8/2.2 mm on the left looking benign (Figure 2); no further imaging was recommended.

Figure 2: Sonogram of the thyroid.

Then we looked for an experienced surgeon who was performing 3-5 pituitary procedures per week and found such in New York City, USA, and in the summer of 2023, the transsphenoidal (TSS) surgery of the pituitary adenoma was performed. The pathology confirmed purely GH-secreting pituitary macroadenoma. Three months after surgery her GH level was 0.8 ng/ml which was normal as well as her IGF-1 was 150 ng/ml- normal.

DISCUSSION

We are describing the case of a patient with acromegaly, which we diagnosed earlier than the average time cited in the literature for the diagnosis of this rare disease. Excess secretion of GH is a known cause of resistance to insulin. Increased levels of insulin to overcome this resistance may lead to increased ovarian production of androgens as well as decreasing sex hormone-binding globulin and increasing free testosterone levels, which can result in hirsutism [9,10]. In our patient, as discussed above, her 3-hour postprandial C-peptide was elevated, suggesting increased levels of insulin due to insulin resistance [9]. PCOS can be idiopathic or secondary to other diseases. Up to 50% of patients with acromegaly have a secondary PCOS phenotype [11]. Our patients did not have PCOS.

Acromegaly is usually diagnosed 5-10 years after the GH excess starts due to initially non-specific features of the disease like mild glycemic problems, hypertension, mild headaches, increased sweating, increased hair growth in females, and hypertension, among others [12]. Untreated, the disease has significant morbidity and mortality. The mortality rate is 2-3 times higher, most commonly due to cardiovascular and respiratory diseases [13].

Early diagnosis is critical because the life expectancy of patients with acromegaly if GH/IGF-1 levels normalize after TSS and/or with medications or radiotherapy can be as age-matched controls [14-16]. Factors associated with a worse prognosis include high GH/IGF-1 levels, cardiomyopathy, and HTN. After successful treatment of acromegaly, the soft tissue changes such as swelling, enlarged tongue, thickened skin, acne, carpal tunnel syndrome, goiter, and sexual dysfunction can resolve, and there might be improvement in diabetes mellitus and hypertension. Unfortunately, the bony changes are permanent [16].

We have reported this case to underscore that in the differential diagnosis of patients presenting with hirsutism and secondary amenorrhea, acromegaly should also be considered. Although diagnostic inertia frequently attributes these findings to idiopathic PCOS, which is a common disorder the diagnosis of much rarer diseases like acromegaly should also be excluded early on. As discussed above, in acromegaly, secondary PCOS can happen in up to 50% of patients and might be reversible after treatment of acromegaly [13,15]. In our patient, acromegaly was the cause of hirsutism, and secondary hypogonadism related to GH-secreting macroadenoma was the cause of her secondary amenorrhea. The patient was also diagnosed with secondary hypothyroidism and treated with levothyroxine 100 micrograms a day. Fortunately, the diagnosis of acromegaly was made early, and none of the most serious complications of the disease like cardiovascular, respiratory, or malignant complications, were present in our patient, and her post-TSS GH/IGF-1 normalized.

CONCLUSION

We are presenting a patient who had secondary amenorrhea of relatively short duration, who also had hirsutism, mood abnormalities, increased sweating, and headache, and those abnormalities developed before significant acral growth, glycemic abnormalities, and cardiac symptoms.

Considering early-on acromegaly in patients with hirsutism, secondary amenorrhea, and other nonspecific complaints can lead to earlier diagnosis of this condition, as in the case described, and avoid devastating complications of the growth hormone excess related to the late diagnosis of this rare disease.

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